

TECHNOLOGY OF FUEL PROCESSING .

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Annotation : Details big serially and I kissed you work in release the details q is additional respectively t without stealing of them nodes and items to work possibility open the door for they are dimensions and shape from ji h horse from each other difference to do need Limited to dimensions relatively to be determined n size nominal measure m that is called Nominal size h is exponential aside of exits the beginning b die lib h am service it will Real , finite size and head q a dimensions h am belongs to nominal size between aside What are you doing ? h am it will be done . Dopusk is the difference between the largest and smallest finite size . Or the most of the log thorough processing given on the surface h am g' adir that 's it b dies . G ' adir - these things size and character or g ' och ning to the structure h am cutting of the instrument processing to give to quality it depends . knives governor

Key s themselves: Details , nodes G'adir - that's it of irregularities maximum high league the details tu rum through attachment , type size b i lan type dirty laundry te sh ikkin size connector dimensions , sharp elements , wood cut detail to make for constructions , Details big serially and I kissed you work in release the details q is additional respectively t without stealing of them nodes and items to work possibility open the door for they are dimensions and shape from ji h horse from each other difference to do need Of this for details and nodes in preparation GOST 6449-76 " Or from hunger and or hungry from materials made items . Doubts and " Transfers " . Yes done normative to the dupusks q at'iy compliance q hangs .

Details , nodes and of items dimensions h am shape from the drawing it will be done . Details collection in time one detail two sisters in detail if he enters , he h ahead connected of parts dimensions connector dimensions that is called For example , details tu rum through in attachment of my type size b i lan type dirty laundry te sh ikkin size connector dimensions b dies . Of the de tals not contiguous dimensions free size that is called Directly measure yu li with oli n gan dimensions real size that is called Road q ' is engraved on the border two size finite size it is said ; real size die q ' is engraved that's it dimensions in intermediate g' i b dies (h a q iqiy size finite to size mo s coming mum k in).

In relation to the finite dimensions, the dimension n is defined as the nominal dimension m is called The nominal size also serves as the starting point for statistical deviations . Deviations between the actual , finite size and other dimensions and the corresponding nominal size are also taken into account. Dopusk is the difference between the largest and smallest finite size . For example, if the nominal y -thickness of the part and the limit 15 mm deviation $\pm 0,2$ mm b are , then the largest finite size (the largest y- thickness) is $15 + 0.2 =$

15,2 mm, and the smallest finite size (the smallest y- thickness) is $15 - 0.2=14.8$ mm b ' can die . In this example, dopusk = $15.2-14.8$ 0,4 mm.

Collect details and q is attached flexibly (stressed) or inflexibly (stressed) . The parts that are flexibly attached are moved to a certain extent relative to each other . Surface q i in the system of suspensions and transfers The term "shaft" is used for (bounding) elements, and the term " hole" is used for internal (encompassing) elements of details. If the size of the hole is larger than the size of the shaft , a gap will appear between their walls, and if the size of the shaft is larger than the size of the hole , tension will be created between them . The term " fire " refers to the character of the joining of details , which is determined by the size of the stress or strain produced at the point of attachment . Alignment of joint bore and shaft bushings dopuski h is calculated . It 's a time of yearning that can be both stressful and stressful . It is called drilling (in this case, the area of the holes and shafts is closed with q or t). In the construction of products, in order to unify them and increase their efficiency, it is necessary to reasonably limit the number of firings . GOST 6449-76 includes nine qualities for calculating gaps in the construction of wooden products (10, 11, ... , 18). The quality of the connecting dimensions should be selected at the same time as the quality of the transitions ; it is calculated based on the required values of the transfer parameters (stress transfer and tension transfer parameters) .

Or the most of the log thorough processing given on the surface h am g' adir - that 's it b dies . G ' adir - these things size and character or g ' och ning to the structure h am cutting of the instrument processing to give to quality it depends . . Wood surface g' adir - that 's it According to GOST 7016-75 according to q b 's death it is necessary G'adir - that's it of irregularities maximum high league Rz_{max} (unevenness from the ch axis concave to the place b is dead ma sofa) average arithmetic size with is characterized and q in the house formula according to b h is calculated as :

$$Rz_{max} = N_{max1} + N_{max2} + N_{taxp} / p$$

this on the ground $N_{max1}, N_{max2} \dots, N_{maxp} / p$ is the maximum irregularities big league p — measured irregularities the number

in table 1 Rz_{max} to 1st-12th grades of size mo s will come _ number the virtues of given

The roughness of the surface is $Rz_{max} \mu m$

1 -j adval

Classes	$Rz_{max} \mu m$ at most	Classes	$Rz_{max} \mu m$ at most
1	1600	7	100
2	1200	8	60
3	800	9	32
4	500	10	16
5	320	11	8
6	200	12	4

Using appropriate methods and processing modes, when processing wood with a well-prepared tool, it is possible to create a surface that corresponds to the following roughness values :

Q value $Rz_{max} = 60 \mu m$ up to has been ghadir - they are TSP 4 device using , the value is $60 \mu m$ from less has been ghadir - that 's it while MIS -11 microscope using is measured . Work

release conditions or hungry of the surface That 's what it's like , often , it 's a good thing given the surface benchmarks to the surface by hanging ta qq hit q it will be flat . Details how get up or from hunger prepared and to the surface q is like that processing given If b dies , standards h am so b 's death it is necessary of the surface t o ' l q humanity and stiffness k ' z with I 'm sorry will be checked .

To the details processing to give to ani q liga of the lathe geometric ani q ligi , t o ' ri correctness and good adjusted k o ' p effect k ' shows .

Geometric precision lathe elements do n't shoot mutually parallelism or perpendicularity , tables and carriages sur ganda their sat h 's o ' change h am of shafts shoot and please according to b kick with is characterized . Machine tools geomet ric accuracy their thorough prepared h am e warm up level it depends . Machine tools three kla s sga : high ori ani q lik , average accuracy and low of the same size to lathes b is measured .

Fat loss in enterprises average _ and low accuracy to pears disc with a saw machines , top accuracy and average accuracy to lathes while milling , longitudinally milling and drill lathes enters

Machine tool elements geometric right away norms t die mo s coming hanging installation and ma h from reduction consists of The workers of the machine shop adjust the machine from time to time . Adjusters check the alignment and compression devices , push mechanisms relative to each other , the straight line movement of the carriages , parallelism and flatness of the tables, plates and alignment devices , they eliminate kicking of shafts and spindles . Adjusters also perform the work of installing the sensors of the control devices on the machines , surrounding the machines with trees, and adjusting the lubrication devices of the machines . Although special workers are involved in adjusting the machine tool, it is necessary for the machine tool operator to know the basic concepts of adjustment in order to eliminate the defects that occur when the machine tool is not adjusted .

necessary to know how to distinguish the adjustment of the machine from its adjustment , in which the adjustment of the machine is done by the machine tool itself . Before processing each new batch of zagotovka , the machine tool adjusts its machine , i.e. sets its support and guide parts , cutting tools and devices in a certain position relative to each other .

the Russian Federation and the Commonwealth of Nations what is going on or go hungry processing to give to sta pears indexes , that is number and h from the harps consists of conditional characters he thinks . _ Index first (sometimes two) h harps of the lathe type means , for example : L g'ulabur saw , Ts — disk sawed , S — grating lathe (reimusli y o' nish , t o ' rt bilaterally according to b milling) , F milling , Sh form shearing , Shl — grinding , SV drilling , T tartar y o' na lada disc with a saw machine tools .

Index second and the third letters h of the lathe to himself special features means : LS — gho ' labor with a saw carpentry lathe TsD is a board wishing disc with a saw lathe ; TsDK — or go conveyor method pushable the same so lathe ; SG — Reismus Lee lathe ; FT milling o gir lathe

Index the third h harp push type or his mechanism represents : SFK — or g'ach conveyor method pushable y o' nish lathe FSA is a form cutting carriage b is dead average _ powerful milling lathe TsPA support automatic to be pushed , k o ' n dalam sawing disc with a saw lathe and h occasion . Index the first from h arfi (or initial two after h arfi) next numbers of the lathe main parameters or cutting of tools the number means : S 2 R 8— table width 8 dm b dead , two bilaterally processing giving reimusli lathe ; SRZ — table width 3 dm b is

dead reimusli lathe ; S 16— table width 16 cm b ' died , t ' rt bilaterally processing gives gan , b ' thought milling lathe and h occasion . Some of machine tools conditional signs , that is index i statement q is hung to the principle t thief doesn't come , for example TsME from ten to g sawing disc sawed , lever - hinged suspension with support lathe

Cutting or cutting of materials necessary measure in ml and shaped details make main is a method . Cutting in the process pone-like sharp or go hungry carve come in or hungry fibers cuts and they are in between to join break , wood known q atlamini , i.e qi rindini cuts Wood q pus without separating cutting h am possible : for example , veneering invalid the name of q when cutting or veneer scissors with at the end of the day q pus does not come out . Energy n i less by spending and ji h oz high fruit with work in detail demand q is hung in quality processing to give for cutting conditions t thief choose know that for while initially this of the process mo h ability to know z

Cutter elements , wood cut detail to make for construction from ji h ati various b is dead one kekichli (knives) , one n echa with a chisel (mills) or k o ' p chisels (saws) as bobs is used (Figure 3).

Figure 1.

Parts of the cutter, surfaces and planes formed when the cutter moves in a straight line (a) and circular (b):

1-machined surface, 2-machined surface, 3-cutting surface, 4-cutting plane, 5-angle measuring plane.

Cutter (1 - ra s m, a) has a pin- shaped shape. The front edge of the cutter is abdf , the back edge is f and two side edges abc and fde there is The front edge of the zagotovka is on the side where the pus comes out , and the back edge is facing the treated surface .

Rakhs are made up of cutting edges ; The cutting edge of the front blade (the tip of the blade) is considered to be dead . If the width of the cutter is narrower than the width of the material b , then not the front edge, but the side edges a and fd too cutting may occur . In this case , along with the front blade , the side blades are also involved in cutting the material . During the cutting process , the surfaces of the zagotovka house q are distinguished :

wooden layer is separated from the processed surface 1 in one (when sharp forward movement) or several (when sharp internal rotation is moving);

treated surface 2 - it is produced after grinding;

cutting surface 3 - forms the cutting edge of the chisel in the processed zagotovka. The knife is more advanced than the zagotovka. When working, it corresponds to the processed surface of the workpiece and the cutting surface. When the cutter rotates cutting the surface the curve is always q , the work of the zagotovka is being performed and processed and the surfaces are flat b may die.

edge of the cutter is back, trying to cut the surface the crossed surface 4 is called the cutting edge. The cutting plane coincides with the cutting surface when the cutting edge is moved. When the cutter rotates, a certain cutting plane corresponds to each of its situations.

Cutting angles. Zago bowl when cutting, the following angles are formed:

sharpening angle b - between the front and back edges of the cutting edge;

the cutting angle s - is formed by the cutting plane with the front edge of the cut;

front angle g - between the edge of the cutter and the perpendicular cutting plane;

cutting angle a is formed by the cutting plane with the cutting edge of the cutting edge.

angles in a plane perpendicular to the cutting plane and corresponding to the direction of movement of the cutter. When working with a rotary cutter, a line that is tangent to the cutting plane at each given point is considered the direction of movement of the cutter.

Depending on how the direction of movement of the cutter is located in relation to the direction of the wood fibers, cutting cases are divided into three: transverse cutting, longitudinal cutting and cutting in the direction transverse to the fibers.

The frame is the base of the machine, and all components and details are fixed to the frame. The frame receives impact forces, vibration loads and the load of the material being processed between some elements of the machine tool.

The frames are made by welding and welding. They are made by filling them with poplar, and the cross-section is usually box-shaped, at the same time, providing the necessary type of flour. The shape and dimensions of the lathes depend on the function and construction of the lathe.

Cutting tools are the working bodies of rotary machines spindles, blades, and shafts on which saws are installed to grind and rotate these tools. service is provided. In machines with a forward movement of the cutting tool, the working bodies are designed either to lock the cutting tool, or to lock it and transmit a linear cutting movement to it, or to push it in the right direction. The working bodies of machines with a hole saw and a grinding belt - pulleys rotate, the cutting tool, that is, a hole saw or a grinding belt, moves forward relative to the zagotovka.

The working or other bodies of the machine are attached to the supports. Depending on the construction of the machine, the work bodies attached to the support are one (for example, vertical); direction, in two (vertical and horizontal) or three directions and can be pushed by the angle h .

In positioning machines, supports are also used for the purpose of reducing support elements - tables. In such machines, the supports sometimes also serve to transmit the push movement to the zagotovka.

In gear-cutting machines, the push mechanisms transmit a continuous uniform movement to the gears; and in the case of positional processing machines, these mechanisms feed the -

cutting tool or the cutting tool, or both the cutting tool and the tool at the same time . h arakat - pushing h a rakat and the direct movement of the mechanism is transmitted.

The drive motor and the intermediate links connecting it to the machine tool elements (for example, a belt drive or a wire shaft to an electric drive consists of a clutch that connects the blades to the shaft). Sometimes, for example, when the shaft of an electric motor - serves as a saw and a saw at the same time, there is no need for intermediate links .

Controls are designed to start and stop the operations of working parts. In modern model machines, operations are controlled automatically and semi-automatically ; some processes start and stop at a specific, predetermined sequence, or at a specific trigger state . Most machine tool control systems provide for automatic stoppage of a malfunction.

The supporting and guiding elements of the machine tools ensure the stability of the zagotovka during the processing process and adjust the pushed zagotovka to the cutting tool.

In positioning processing, clamps fix the zagotovka in a certain situation. Clamping devices ensure tight contact of the zagotovka with the guide during passing operations. Pillars helps to position the zagotovka correctly in a specific situation relative to the cutting tool . Supply and loading devices transfer workpieces to the machine and take processed workpieces or parts from the machine and place them in transport packages.

Sharpening devices are intended for sharpening and correcting the shape of the cutting tool directly on the machine.

Adjustment devices are available on all machines . They are in the position of the guide and the cutting tool of the supporting elements compression and transmission, the basis of the elements to qi cms is used to change the relative situation .

Waste disposal devices consist of exhaust receivers and are connected to pipes that remove dust , scum , and scum generated during furnace processing . Lubricants are used to lubricate working surfaces .

organ of disc saws and aggregate machines . Saw shaft casings² ra installed two ball bearings rotate in 3 , the shaft to the base of the machine tool (for example, to the machine) with the help of these housings installed . A pulley is reduced to one end of the shaft by 1 ma h ; the rotation of the electric motor is transmitted to the shaft through a belt attached to this shaft . On the other end of the shaft, a disc saw 5 is taken between special washers 6 and 4 , and it is tightened with a nut 7. The washer 4 is fixed to the shaft , usually with a prismatic key, and the washer 6 is fixed with a sliding washer . The disc saw tightening nut 7 should be tightened by turning it in the opposite direction to the direction of rotation of the disc saw, so that it does not twist during the work process . Therefore , the thread at the end of the saw shaft can be right- handed or left - handed , depending on the direction of rotation of the shaft . In some designs of circular saw machines (balancer and draw -pendulum) both housings of the saw shaft ball bearing housings are integrally carved and hinged to the barrel or consist of a single frame that turns on a fixed axis .

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